

Quantitative morphological analysis of warp and weft yarns in historical woven structures

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[link to a short video abstract](#)

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Abstract

The research in this paper proposes a set of methods for obtaining measurable data describing the yarns in historical textiles, as quantitative knowledge of their characteristics is currently lacking in conservation and conservation science. A group of 26 samples, mostly from historical paintings of known provenance, were studied using a systematic approach to their analysis, and novel methods to measure crimp, twist, yarn width and thickness. Thread count, thickness, weight and pH of the textile were also measured. Describing such a wealth of characteristics with quantitative measurements has made it possible to gain a better understanding of traditional textiles and their production. Working with numerical data makes it possible to compare the structures of different fabrics and to estimate the stiffness or the tendency to creep of historical textiles.

Correlations have been established between the measured characteristics of the interlaced yarns and the warp and weft directions, which appear to be uncontroversial within this group of samples. Increasing the number of textiles analysed with the proposed protocol will improve the ability to distinguish warp and weft when a selvedge is not available. This is made possible with a mostly non-destructive analysis of a small sample, as the extraction of only a few yarns is needed to measure yarn crimp and thickness. This approach allows obtaining, for historical woven structures, the data needed for textile engineering studies, and new opportunities for their analysis and for predictive digital simulations are offered. The next step of the ongoing research will be to establish correlations with the tensile response of the 26 textiles analysed.

Introduction and general definitions

The structure and internal morphology of textiles are determined during their manufacture. A strand of fibre is spun into a yarn, and twisting gives it the cohesion and tensile strength needed for weaving. During the weaving process, the warp yarns are kept under tension on the loom and run parallel to the length of the fabric. They are divided into sets to create an open space, or shed, through which the weft runs before the warp sets are inverted to create a new shed. During weaving, the yarns intertwine and the resulting pressure changes their shape from straight to wavy. This waviness, or crimp, means that more yarn is needed to cover the distance between the ends of the fabric. The pressure also causes the cross-section of the yarn to change from roughly circular to elliptical, which is described by the length of the two axes rather than simply a radius. All these aspects are commonly quantified in textile industry research [Pierce, 1937; Behera et al., 2010; Neckář and Das, 2018] allowing predictive models and structural comparisons between different fabrics. At the first level of observation, the type of woven structure (plain weave or other), the thickness of the textile, its weight/m² and the number of yarns/cm are required for comparisons. The weight per unit length of

the yarns, the type of fibre and the number of twists per unit of length, the percentage of crimp the yarns undergo during weaving, and the description of their cross-section, are all included in the list of the standard quantitative observations.

Much less detailed data is available when it comes to historical canvas supports. This is due to the fact that it is not as easy to take samples from a historical artifact as it is from a new industrial product, and also because a canvas support is typically impregnated with size and preparation layers or substances deriving from treatments. The only data usually available are the type of weave, the thread-count and the nature of the fibres. The presence of paint layers and other contaminants even limits measurements of the weight per unit area and the thickness of the textile. Most other measurements are complicated by the variability of historical materials and their limited availability for sampling. The weight of the yarn per unit length is a perfect example because clean yarns of sufficient length¹ are simply not available in conservation. The cross-section of historical yarns is very uneven along their length when compared to industrially spun yarns. It is therefore much more complex to provide a repeatable value, and often only the width is measured, and not the length of the minor axis. The pH and the degree of polymerization of the cellulose are sometimes measured in conservation science as indicators of degradation processes and, when available, can be used to back-up treatment decisions.

Twist and crimp measurements form a group of their own, as they are among the most relevant characteristics of a woven structure, and have always been the object of textile technology studies [Pierce, 1937; Mertova et al., 2016; Neckář and Das, 2019]. Detailed technological descriptions of ancient textiles, including measurements of twist and crimp, are rare. A rather exceptional case is [Berry et al., 78], which describes a rich archaeological find (more than 150 kg of raw textiles), that allowed for extensive sampling and invasive testing, making it possible to apply the textile engineering approaches to the measurement of twist, crimp, and even weight per unit length. Nevertheless, the elliptical yarn cross-section was characterised by the major axis alone (defined as the yarn diameter) and the minor axis was not mentioned.

The standard method of measuring twist in a yarn is to untwist it and count the number of turns required to revert the fibres to their original state, parallel to the yarn axis [Saville, 1999]. In general, the method is not applicable to historical textiles, because the yarns are either too fragile to withstand untwisting or impregnated with substances that would not allow it. Observation based methods are used to measure the "twist angle", as described in handbooks [Seiler-Baldinger, 1996], papers [Rouba, 1992], archaeological reports [Ostergard, 2004] and in studies dedicated to thread-by-thread tear mending [Flock, 2020]. However, the twist angle is a semi-qualitative value as the actual number of twists per meter in a yarn, obtained through the correlation of the angle with the width of the yarn, is not provided. A method that allows the correlation between the twist angle and the actual count of the twists per unit of length² to be made [Conti and Tassinari, 1973] has only recently been used in conservation science [Iaccarino Idelson et al., 2024].

The standard method for measuring crimp is also mechanical, based on uncrimping the yarn by pulling it straight to calculate the difference in length [Kovar, 2011], and this is also not possible for

¹ The standard reference is the Tex, a direct measure of linear density, providing the weight in grams per 1 kilometre of yarn. Industrial yarns are weighed when rolled on bobbin, a simple operation with the additional advantage of lowering the error due to the length of the sample. When dealing with historical textiles, the length of the yarns available for weight measurement are often no more than a few centimetres and they are often contaminated with substances that affect their weight.

² Original text in Italian available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13949451> ; English translation available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13949377>

naturally aged or impregnated yarns. The path the yarn travels in the textile can be calculated by analysing its waveform in the cross section of the fabric [Mertova et al., 2016] (see fig. 1) or by observing the image of individual yarns [Young and Jardine, 2012], as geometric simplifications provide reliable data for modern textiles, when they have a very constant waveform. An alternative optical method is based on drawing a line on the neutral axis of the yarn using specialized software [Kolcavova Sirkova & Vysanska 2012]. This approach was found to be the most suitable for describing irregular crimp configurations and was used for the study of historical yarns [Iaccarino Idelson et al., 2024].

Figure 1. Typical elliptical cross-section of the yarns of a historical sample (credit Giorgia Agresti).

The most comprehensive descriptions available for the canvas supports of paintings are obtained from the analysis of X-ray images and provide information on the density, position and direction of the yarns on the entire painting [van de Wetering, 1997; Johnson, et al., 2013; Nobel et al., 2018]. The elaboration of such observations also allows the identification of warp and weft directions, based on the variability of the thread count, the thread angle within the textile and the presence of specific irregularities in the weaving. In the textile industry, automated methods to obtain the thread count from the image of a textile have been developed [Pan, et al. 2015; Aldemir, et al., 2018]. Although very useful for technical art history and for industrial inspection, these methods do not provide the quantitative data that make the subject of the present research.

Such limitation contributes to the above-mentioned lack of numerical data describing morphological characteristics such as crimp, twist and yarn dimensions for historical textiles. Still, numerical data is necessary to build detailed FEM simulations and when seeking correlations between the mechanical behaviour of historical textiles in tensile tests. This is currently being done by the author on the specimens examined in the present study, whose tensile response is being measured using the biaxial tester, described in [Iaccarino Idelson et al., 2023].

Aim of the paper and research questions

The methodological study proposed here aims at a systematic approach to the analysis of the woven structure of canvas painting supports with reference to textile engineering. The first research question is whether it is possible to obtain quantitative data on the woven structure of historical textiles. Such an opening would expand the possibilities for understanding their mechanical behaviour and improve the assessment of conservation conditions. Characteristics such as yarn dimensions, twist, crimp, and even thickness and weight/m², present specific difficulties when dealing with a sample that is highly variable, limited in quantity, degraded, and contaminated. The organization of simple statistical methods for data collection is also a relevant subject, since the goal is to allow comparisons.

The second research question is whether it is possible to find recurring characteristics that can provide a degree of confidence in the identification of warp and weft yarns when a selvedge is not available. This seems to be a relatively urgent need, since the mechanical behaviour of the textile is different in the two directions [Young and Hibberd, 1999], and their identification is relevant for conservation and research purposes [Rouba, 1980; van de Wetering, 1997; Johnson, et al., 2013; Nobel et al., 2018].

Materials and methods

The group of samples, their preparation and statistical data collection

The need for this study arose when approaching the mechanical examination of a group of textiles with uniaxial and biaxial tensile tests using the above-mentioned device [Iaccarino Idelson et al., 2023]. A group of "plain weave" fabrics³ without paint layers was selected, all of which have a selvedge to ensure that warp and weft can be reliably identified in order to define the related tensile response. Most of the specimens (22 out of 26) are naturally aged, some with known provenance, date, and artist. These were extracted from paintings (dating from 1728 to the 1950s) during past conservation treatments, and 12 of them represent a relatively homogeneous group of mid-to-late 19th century French artworks. Lining and loose lining canvases between the 18th and 19th centuries⁴, and four modern canvases complete the set. Three of these are industrially woven lining canvases: two are typical open-weave paste-glue lining canvases, the Italian "patta" and "pattina", from a 2015 lot; the basket weave canvas used in the making of a mock-up of Rembrandt's *The Night Watch*; the manually woven replica of a traditional canvas used by Dutch old masters produced in 2022 within the NICAS project⁵ "Canvassing the making". The complete list is in Table 1, also including their weight per square meter and pH, provided as the mean of the values obtained on multiple samples from the same specimen.

name	general data			weight measures in grams							g/sqm	pH
	date	fibers	manufacture	sample 1	sample 2	sample 3	sample 4	mean	st. dev.			
1 plain canvas 1	18th c.	linen	hand	0,076	0,073	0,077	0,079	0,08	0,003	257	6,5	
2 plain canvas 2	18th c.	linen	hand	0,130	0,129	0,134	0,125	0,13	0,004	435	6,1	
3 plain canvas 3	18th c.	linen	hand	0,068	0,085	0,091	0,086	0,08	0,010	278	6,4	
4 plain canvas 4	18th c.	hemp	hand	0,101	0,100	0,092	0,098	0,10	0,004	329	7,4	
5 plain canvas 5	19th c.	hemp	hand	0,132	0,132	0,133	0,131	0,13	0,001	445	7,3	
6 Domenico C. Malinconico	1728	hemp	hand	0,083	0,076	0,059	-	0,07	0,013	244	6,2	
7 Bernard d'Agesci	1817	hemp	hand	0,151	0,126	0,048	0,071	0,10	0,048	334	6,8	
8 medium paste lining canvas (IT)	early 19th c.	hemp	machine	0,055	0,047	0,051	0,044	0,05	0,005	166	6,0	
9 heavy paste lining canvas (IT)	early 19th c.	linen	machine	0,179	0,189	0,193	-	0,19	0,007	628	6,0	
10 Fragonard medium paste lining	mid 19th c.	hemp	machine	0,120	0,118	0,113	0,122	0,12	0,004	397	6,1	
11 Raffaele Postiglione	1845	linen	hand	0,083	0,080	0,076	0,075	0,08	0,004	265	5,2	
12 Alfred Dehodencq	1870	linen	machine	0,094	0,097	0,102	0,094	0,10	0,004	326	5,6	
13 Jules Géliibert	1881	linen	machine	0,073	0,072	0,071	0,068	0,07	0,002	238	5,8	
14 Louis Augustin Auguin	1885	linen	machine	0,088	0,091	0,085	0,089	0,09	0,003	296	6,1	
15 Ludovic Alleaume	1887	linen	machine	0,072	0,074	0,073	0,076	0,07	0,002	248	5,2	
16 Hubert Sauzeau 1	1893	linen	machine	0,058	0,065	0,060	0,060	0,06	0,003	205	6,2	
17 Hubert Sauzeau 2	1898	hemp	machine	0,138	0,152	0,150	0,136	0,14	0,008	485	6,6	
18 Charles Müller	late 19th c.	linen	machine	0,042	0,047	0,044	0,046	0,04	0,002	150	5,6	
19 Furcy de Lavault	late 19th c.	linen	machine	0,067	0,066	0,072	0,066	0,07	0,003	228	6,0	
20 Louis Alexandre Cabié	1905	weft hemp; warp cotton	machine	0,085	0,080	0,082	0,081	0,08	0,002	276	5,9	
21 Louis Lessieux	early 20th c.	hemp	machine	0,068	0,054	0,052	0,061	0,06	0,007	197	6,4	
22 Jeannine Gilles-Murique	mid 20th c.	hemp	machine	0,115	0,122	0,113	0,108	0,11	0,006	385	5,5	
23 Night Watch mockup canvas	1975	linen	machine	0,097	0,096	0,101	0,096	0,10	0,002	380	6,2	
24 "pattina" lining canvas	2015	linen	machine	0,043	0,043	0,047	0,045	0,04	0,002	149	6,5	
25 "patta" lining canvas	2015	linen	machine	0,057	0,051	0,043	0,051	0,05	0,006	171	6,6	
26 canvassing "03f"	2022	linen	hand	0,098	0,103	0,103	0,111	0,10	0,005	349	7,8	

Table 1. General data on the samples, with the weight per square meter and pH.

³ The only exception is made for a "basket weave" canvas, a "plain weave" with two parallel yarns. The canvas was added to the group because it was deeply studied in a parallel project.

⁴ Among them the canvas used by A.E. Fragonard for his "François 1er armé chevalier par Bayard" to adapt its dimensions when it was first exhibited in the Louvre Museum in 1829

⁵ Project directed by Prof. dr. R.G. Erdmann (University of Amsterdam/Rijksmuseum), with S.A.F. Smelt (Rijksmuseum); I. Meijssen (Ingeborg Meijssen Textiles); L. Hassink (Museum Bussemakerhuis); I. Verslype (Rijksmuseum). <https://www.nicas-research.nl/projects/canvassing-the-making/>

Since they will be subjected to tensile tests, samples were laser cut following the cruciform patterns described in [Iaccarino Idelson et. al., 23]. Laser cutting causes only a very localised burning of the yarns⁶ while offering the considerable advantage of avoiding the mechanical stresses on the textile caused by any blade cutting method (see fig. 2). Laser cutting from a CAD design provides a precise and repeatable measure of the area of the sample, that was used to calculate the weight of the textile in grams/m². The sharp 10x10mm testing area was photographed at high-resolution⁷ and scaled to the real dimensions, to take precision measurements of the individual yarns with the support of a CAD⁸ software. As a consistent area of observation is defined thanks to the CAD design of the laser cut⁹, a weighted mean was calculated instead of a simple mean, after dividing the yarns in warp and weft in three subsets for relative dimensions (Small, Medium and Large). One yarn from each subset, chosen as the most representative, was measured at three locations using the procedure described in the next section. The mean value of the measures for the chosen yarn in each subset (fig. 3) was used to calculate the weighted mean. As this is the sum of the value obtained for each chosen yarn times the number of yarns in each subset, divided for the number of yarns in warp or weft, the process results in a matrix of 9 measures in warp and 9 in weft. This describes the value of a specific feature in each 1 cm² area of observation, and the standard deviation provides a measure of its variability.

Figure 2. The image of one of the laser-cut samples (n. 2 in table 1), with the indentations in the weft direction.

⁶ The well focused laser beam is very thin, thus causing only local heating. When dealing with cellulosic fibres, the affected part of the textile sublimates, the perimeter is carbonised and no sealing effect is visible, as the residual dust falls off spontaneously.

⁷ Images taken with a 2:1 macro lens. When cropped close to the sample perimeter, as in fig. 2, a square image measuring 21.7mm contains 3230 pixels per side, at a resolution of 6.7 micron/pixel.

⁸ Rhinoceros, Robert McNeel & Associates version 7 was used, but the same tools are found in earlier versions and in other software such as Autocad, and in libreware and non-proprietary applications. The method is described in the next section.

⁹ The same result could be obtained inserting a scale bar in the image.

Figure 3. Example of the observations on the subsets. Yarns in warp (red) and weft (green) chosen to represent the Small-Medium-Large subsets in the 1cm² sample.

Measuring procedures

Weight and thickness of the canvas, weight of the yarns, and thread-count

The samples were weighed¹⁰ using a certified analytical scale¹¹ with a resolution of 0.1 mg and a repeatability of +/- 0.05 mg. As the sample surface is a given information thanks to the laser-cutting procedure¹², a simple calculation provided the weight in g/m², averaging the weight of 4 samples¹³. The thickness of the canvas was measured using a 6 mm diameter flat-end micrometre with a resolution of 0.001 mm. The “friction drive” was used, which slips when the set pressure is reached, allowing the spindle to stop moving even if the user continues to turn the thimble¹⁴. The same, very low, compression force was applied on all samples. Measurements were repeated at 5 points on each of the 3 selected samples. Since the length of the pieces of yarn that can be extracted from the specimens is not more than 20 or 30 mm, their weight happens to be too close to the lower limit of the analytical scale (0.1 mg). For this reason, after a few attempts with yarns from different specimens, it was decided to exclude this information from the set of data collected in this research. Thread-count in both directions was counted under magnification at three locations in different samples. The information is correlated to each sample, and the general mean and standard deviation are given.

Identification of fibres

Individual fibres were extracted¹⁵ from the yarn and mechanically separated using a specillum. A sample was prepared for observation under a mineralogical optical microscope using an object slide, Canada balsam, and object coverslip. The preparations thus obtained were observed under the Zeiss Axioskop polarizing optical microscope with the Zeiss Axio Cam NRc camera attached, and the images were processed using Axio Vision processing software. The analysis of the morphological

¹⁰ Environmental data: Temperature 20°C (+/- 1), and Relative Humidity 50% (+/- 5).

¹¹ Gibertini ETERNITY 100 SMI.

¹² The total area of a cruciform sample, with the indentations in the weft arms, is 297.12 mm².

¹³ For specimens 6 and 9 only 3 samples were available.

¹⁴ Micrometre model SXQFC-001eu, Beslands. Though the very low value of approx. 0.02 N/cm² was measured for the compression force, a certain crushing of the sample, not noticeable during the tests, must be taken into account.

¹⁵ The identification of the fibres was carried out at the Università della Tuscia, Viterbo, Group of Diagnostics and Materials Science, by Dr. Giorgia Agresti and Prof. Ulderico Santamaria.

characteristics of the fibres was performed for comparison with databases in the literature [Markova, 2019].

pH measures

Measures of pH of an insoluble solid material require bringing free ions into solution in order to read the H^+ concentration. Depending on the type of electrode chosen, it will either be immersed in the liquid phase or measure the pH of a thin liquid film on the surface of the solid. Immersion of the textile sample in the liquid phase is among the standard procedures for textiles¹⁶, and although it involves the destruction of the sample, it was not ruled out as it could be performed after the tensile tests. However, preliminary tests showed that the pH of the liquid phase continued to fluctuate for a long time, probably due to the gradual solubilisation of materials in the historical canvas, and even more so when testing a canvas with layers of preparation and paint. The immersion method was not selected, because the results seemed to be easily influenced by unpredictable factors. A recently developed alternative method is to measure the pH of an agarose gel used to extract free ions from the surface [Rota et al., 2021], limiting the diffusion of water into the material. The method is extremely useful for fragile textiles¹⁷ and is also used on paintings¹⁸. Nevertheless, after careful evaluation of the options, an intermediate approach was chosen, as in [Böhme et al., 2020], based on the use of a contact pH meter with a drop of water placed on the sample¹⁹. The method used to be the standard approach before the introduction of the agarose gels, and was successfully used on canvas paintings over the past decade²⁰. The advantage is that it seems to allow the extraction of more ions from below the surface if compared with the agarose gel, thus providing values with a wider distribution. If compared with the method based on the immersion of the sample, the pH value stabilises within 3 to 5 minutes, and values appeared to be more repeatable. Of course, the problem is not one offering a single solution, and all methods currently used in conservation practice and conservation science have advantages and limitations.

Yarn width assessment

The long axis of the elliptical cross-section of the yarns (fig.1) can be measured by a completely non-destructive observation of the surface of the textile²¹. Free access to a large number of measuring points allows the weighted mean to be calculated. Within the 1 cm² area of the digital image, the yarns were grouped in the 3 subsets in warp and 3 in weft. A representative yarn in each subset was identified and measured at 3 different locations, by tracing the tangent on the side of the yarn, then offset to the opposite side including its width (lines 1 and 2 in fig. 4). The weighted mean and standard deviation were then calculated. The measurement of the short axis of the elliptical cross section of the yarns (fig.1) requires them to be extracted from the textile in order to observe them from the side. As this destructive operation is also needed for the measurement of the crimp value, the two were carried out on the same yarns, and will be described later.

¹⁶ An early example is found in [British Standard Handbook n.11, 1963]. Updated versions are ISO-3071-2020 and ISO 6588-1:2021.

¹⁷ In recent years it has become the standard procedure at the Abegg-Stiftung textile conservation studio (this was learned during a private communication).

¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bOqZEE7Kb8Y>

¹⁹ See the Tappi T 529 standard (1999).

²⁰ This is a professional statement of the author, who used the method to measure the pH of paintings in conservation practice since 2013.

²¹ Measures were taken on the unstretched, laser cut samples. It would be interesting to repeat the measures on samples stretched under a known value of tension, and a reduction of the value is expected.

Twist measures

Twist measurements are taken on the same yarns and at the same locations as those selected for the width measurements. A diagonal line is drawn (line 4, in fig. 4) following the direction of the twisted fibres visible on the surface, as when measuring the “twist angle” [Seiler-Baldinger, 1996]; the adjacent segment, line 3, drawn at the intersection between lines 4 and 2, represents the yarn width and closes a right-angle triangle in which the second cathetus is named “ L ”. The length of L (in mm) is used to calculate the twists per meter (TPM) at a given point on the yarn according to the simple equation: $TPM=318/L$. For a complete description and demonstration, see [Conti and Tassinari, 1973] and the English translation available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13949377>. For its application and further validation see [Iaccarino Idelson et al., 2024]. The twist direction (Z or S) is recorded, the weighted mean of the TPM and the standard deviation are calculated.

Figure 4. The geometries used to measure yarn width (lines 1, 2) and twist (lines 3, 4 and segment L).

Crimp measures and yarn thickness

The procedure requires the extraction of 3 yarn fragments in both warp and weft, which are photographed in high resolution and scaled to their real dimensions in CAD. The polyline P is drawn in the middle of the yarn, along its neutral axis (fig. 5), and the straight-line T , connecting its ends along the plane of the textile, is used to calculate the crimp % according to the standard equation [1].

$$\text{Crimp \%} = \frac{P-T}{P} \times 100 \quad [1]$$

To measure crimp on the same yarns described for width and twist measurements, it would be necessary to completely disassemble the textile. As this would imply the loss of correlation with the mechanical behaviour of the sample under tensile testing, the decision was made to use neighbouring yarns from the textile around the laser-cut perimeter. The available yarns were 8 to 25 mm long, thus providing a value that represents the mean of the waveform along their path, and the mean and the standard deviation were calculated. A more detailed description of the crimp measurement method including a further level of validation, based on [Kovar, 2011; Mertova et al., 2016], is in [Iaccarino Idelson et al.,].

The image in fig. 5 shows a yarn along the z axis, orthogonal to the (x-y) plane of the textile seen in fig.5. The z axis image is necessary to measure the, otherwise invisible, thickness of the yarns. Using similar CAD procedures, at least 3 thickness measurements were taken from each of the same yarns

used to calculate the crimp. The mean and the standard deviation of at least 9 measurements in warp and 9 in weft measurements of the yarn thickness were calculated.

Figure 5. The geometry involved in the measures of crimp (lines P and T) and of yarn thickness.

Experimental results

Weight and thickness of the canvas, thread-count, fibre identification and pH

The values of the weight of the samples, their mean and standard deviation are found in table 1, along with the nature of the fibres and pH measures. The thickness of the canvas samples, was measured at 5 points in 4 units, and the general mean values of the 20 measurements and their standard deviation are given in table 2. The number of yarns per cm was counted at three locations, in different samples. The general mean values of the readings and their standard deviation are listed in table 3.

name	textile thickness measures					
	sample 1	sample 2	sample 3	sample 4	mm	st. dev.
1 plain canvas 1	0,52	0,59	0,52	0,55	0,54	0,03
2 plain canvas 2	1,01	0,98	1,00	0,92	0,98	0,04
3 plain canvas 3	0,36	0,37	0,32	0,36	0,35	0,02
4 plain canvas 4	0,83	0,82	0,84	0,87	0,84	0,02
5 plain canvas 5	0,87	0,88	0,86	0,87	0,87	0,01
6 Domenico C. Malinconico	0,25	0,27	0,27	0,27	0,26	0,01
7 Bernard d'Agesci	0,47	0,38	0,39	0,38	0,41	0,04
8 medium paste lining canvas (IT)	0,49	0,49	0,47	0,48	0,48	0,01
9 heavy paste lining canvas (IT)	1,32	1,21	1,32	1,28	1,28	0,05
10 Fragonard medium paste lining	0,68	0,65	0,72	0,69	0,68	0,03
11 Raffaele Postiglione	0,77	0,58	0,62	0,66	0,66	0,08
12 Alfred Dehodencq	0,35	0,33	0,29	0,33	0,32	0,03
13 Jules Gélibert	0,47	0,45	0,46	0,44	0,45	0,01
14 Louis Augustin Auguin	0,22	0,22	0,22	0,21	0,22	0,01
15 Ludovic Alleaume	0,44	0,44	0,46	0,44	0,44	0,01
16 Hubert Sauzeau 1	0,38	0,38	0,37	0,38	0,37	0,00
17 Hubert Sauzeau 2	0,78	0,82	0,85	0,80	0,81	0,03
18 Charles Müller	0,25	0,27	0,27	0,27	0,26	0,01
19 Furcy de Lavault	0,38	0,38	0,39	0,37	0,38	0,01
20 Louis Alexandre Cabié	0,28	0,28	0,27	0,29	0,28	0,01
21 Louis Lessieux	0,18	0,18	0,20	0,24	0,20	0,03
22 Jeannine Gilles-Murique	0,80	0,85	0,79	0,75	0,80	0,04
23 Night Watch mockup canvas	0,72	0,71	0,72	0,72	0,72	0,00
24 "pattina" lining canvas	0,45	0,43	0,43	0,44	0,44	0,01
25 "patta" lining canvas	0,60	0,56	0,51	0,57	0,56	0,04
26 canvassing "03f"	0,78	0,82	0,82	0,81	0,81	0,02

Table 2. The thickness of the canvas samples.

name	thread count										
	warp 1	warp 2	warp 3	weft 1	weft 2	weft 3	warp mean	weft mean	warp st. dev.	weft st. dev.	
1 plain canvas 1	16,0	17,0	17,0	13,5	14,0	13,0	16,7	13,5	0,6	0,5	
2 plain canvas 2	12,0	11,0	10,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	11,0	8,0	1,0	0,0	
3 plain canvas 3	14,0	13,0	14,0	12,0	12,0	12,0	13,7	12,0	0,6	0,0	
4 plain canvas 4	9,0	9,0	9,0	7,0	7,0	7,0	9,0	7,0	0,0	0,0	
5 plain canvas 5	17,5	16,0	16,0	11,0	10,0	12,0	16,5	11,0	0,9	1,0	
6 Domenico C. Malinconico	13,0	13,0	13,0	13,0	13,0	13,0	13,0	13,0	0,0	0,0	
7 Bernard d'Agesci	19,0	19,0	18,0	15,5	17,5	18,0	18,7	17,0	0,6	1,3	
8 medium paste lining canvas (IT)	8,0	7,0	8,0	8,0	7,0	8,0	7,7	7,7	0,6	0,6	
9 heavy paste lining canvas (IT)	9,0	8,5	8,5	7,0	7,0	7,0	8,7	7,0	0,3	0,0	
10 Fragonard medium paste lining	14,0	14,0	13,0	11,0	12,0	11,0	13,7	11,3	0,6	0,6	
11 Raffaele Postiglione	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	0,0	0,0	
12 Alfred Dehodencq	17,0	17,0	17,0	11,0	11,0	11,0	17,0	11,0	0,0	0,0	
13 Jules Gélibert	24,0	24,0	24,0	19,0	19,0	18,0	24,0	18,7	0,0	0,6	
14 Louis Augustin Auguin	26,0	24,0	26,0	26,0	24,0	25,0	25,3	25,0	1,2	1,0	
15 Ludovic Alleaume	23,0	25,0	24,0	21,0	22,0	22,0	24,0	21,7	1,0	0,6	
16 Hubert Sauzeau 1	22,0	22,0	22,0	19,0	21,0	20,0	22,0	20,0	0,0	1,0	
17 Hubert Sauzeau 2	14,0	14,0	14,0	12,0	12,0	12,0	14,0	12,0	0,0	0,0	
18 Charles Müller	32,0	32,0	30,0	29,0	29,0	29,0	31,3	29,0	1,2	0,0	
19 Furcy de Lavault	23,5	24,0	23,0	23,0	22,0	22,0	23,5	22,3	0,5	0,6	
20 Louis Alexandre Cabié	11,0	12,0	12,0	10,5	11,0	11,0	11,7	10,8	0,6	0,3	
21 Louis Lessieux	21,0	21,0	21,0	21,0	21,0	21,0	21,0	21,0	0,0	0,0	
22 Jeannine Gilles-Murique	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	8,0	0,0	0,0	
23 Night Watch mockup canvas	20,0	21,0	19,0	15,0	16,0	17,0	20,0	16,0	1,0	1,0	
24 "pattina" lining canvas	9,0	9,0	9,0	9,0	9,0	9,0	9,0	9,0	0,0	0,0	
25 "patta" lining canvas	7,0	7,0	7,0	5,0	5,0	5,0	7,0	5,0	0,0	0,0	
26 canvassing "03f"	12,0	12,0	12,0	7,0	7,0	7,0	12,0	7,0	0,0	0,0	

Table 3. Thread count analysis.

The mean values in warp and weft are compared in fig. 6, and also the difference between the two values is also shown in the histogram. The warp yarns are more numerous than the weft yarns in 20 of the 26 specimens, and the remaining 6 have equal values. This correlation is due to practical considerations on the part of the manufacturer to achieve a balanced textile. As the main cost in the weaving process is the casting of the wefts in the shed, it is preferable to use a higher number of warp yarns to achieve a given density²². In addition, a high weft density produces more tension in the warp, which will unbalance the fabric and cause it to wear out faster in use. A higher thread count in the warp direction is confirmed in most textile engineering literature, as in [Pan et al., 2015].

Figure 6. Thread-count in the two directions. Warp yarns are more numerous than weft yarns, or equal.

²² Special thanks to Clemente Sironi, from the textile company Sironi in Italy, and to the hand-weaver Ingeborg Meijssen for the useful and interesting conversations on this subject.

Yarn width and thickness

The width of the yarns was measured using the geometries described in fig.4, according to the relative dimensional subsets (see fig. 3) in the 1 cm² image of the sample. The data in table 4 describe the variability of the yarns observed in the samples. When the number of the yarns of the middle subset (M) prevails on the others (as in ns. 13; 20; 26 in the warp and in ns. 13; 22; 24 in the weft), the textile has a high dimensional homogeneity. If the S and L subsets have a higher share of the population, the yarn dimensions are more variable. A further evaluation of the variability can be obtained by comparing the measurements in the subsets, using the standard deviation. Specimen n. 10 is a useful example, as the number of yarns in the M subset is predominant, but the S value is almost 4 times smaller than the L in the weft, and 2 times in the warp.

The standard deviation of the width values measured in warp and weft (table 4) allows a comparison with the higher variability of the weft yarn width found in the literature [Rouba, 1992; van de Wetering, 1997; Johnson, et al., 2013; Nobel et al., 2018]. However, the mean values of the standard deviation in warp (0.17 mm) and weft (0.15 mm) and the standard deviation of their values in warp (0.07 mm) and weft (0.08 mm) are too similar to attempt any meaningful consideration of the issue. The standard deviation of the difference between the L and S width values in table 5 are slightly more different in warp (0.11 mm) and in weft (0.14 mm). When the number of the observed samples will be larger, other statistical approaches will be used.

The weighted mean values in warp and in weft are compared in fig. 7, where the difference between the two values is also shown. In the large majority of cases (20 out of 26, or 77%) the warp yarns are wider than the weft yarns. In the 11 cases under the pale blue band in fig. 7, the differences are very shallow: between 0.08 mm and -0.08 mm. If this subset is not included in the general evaluation, the remaining 15 values show more substantial differences (between 13% and 58%). Among these 15, warp yarns are wider in 12 textiles, and only in 3 cases is the opposite true, showing a slightly higher prevalence (80%).

WARP yarn width		dimensional classes numerosity				yarn width means					yarn thickness				
sample name	th. count	S	M	L	S mean	M mean	L mean	w. mean	st. dev.	mean 1	mean 2	mean 3	warp	st. dev.	
1 plain canvas 1	16,7	4	7,7	5	0,30	0,43	0,67	0,47	0,16	0,22	0,17	0,22	0,20	0,03	
2 plain canvas 2	11,0	1	7,0	3	0,56	0,79	1,17	0,87	0,28	0,37	0,24	0,38	0,33	0,08	
3 plain canvas 3	13,7	1	9,7	3	0,53	0,87	1,00	0,87	0,21	0,31	0,27	0,25	0,28	0,03	
4 plain canvas 4	9,0	2	5,0	2	0,53	0,76	1,16	0,80	0,28	0,46	0,59	0,41	0,49	0,09	
5 plain canvas 5	16,5	3	8,5	5	0,39	0,59	0,87	0,64	0,21	0,25	0,24	0,33	0,27	0,05	
6 Domenico C. Malinconico	13,0	2	7,0	4	0,43	0,72	0,80	0,70	0,19	0,28	0,22	0,23	0,24	0,03	
7 Bernard d'Agesci	18,7	1	13,7	4	0,28	0,34	0,58	0,39	0,15	0,21	0,28	0,31	0,27	0,05	
8 medium paste lining canvas (IT)	7,0	2	3,0	2	0,62	0,70	1,11	0,79	0,24	0,39	0,31	0,39	0,36	0,05	
9 heavy paste lining canvas (IT)	8,7	1	5,7	2	0,81	1,18	1,39	1,19	0,25	0,50	0,52	-	0,51	0,01	
10 Fragonard medium paste lining	13,7	1	10,7	2	0,23	0,74	0,88	0,72	0,30	0,33	0,23	0,34	0,30	0,06	
11 Raffaele Postiglione	8,0	1	6,0	1	0,41	0,61	0,76	0,60	0,16	0,34	0,38	0,43	0,38	0,05	
12 Alfred Dehodencq	17,0	2	12,0	3	0,47	0,69	0,94	0,71	0,20	0,33	0,37	0,44	0,38	0,06	
13 Jules Gélibert	24,0	1	22,0	1	0,40	0,49	0,53	0,49	0,09	0,21	0,20	0,20	0,20	0,01	
14 Louis Augustin Auguin	25,0	2	21,0	2	0,33	0,38	0,50	0,39	0,10	0,28	0,23	0,21	0,24	0,04	
15 Ludovic Alleaume	24,0	2	18,0	4	0,30	0,43	0,54	0,44	0,11	0,15	0,18	0,16	0,16	0,02	
16 Hubert Sauzeau 1	22,0	3	15,0	4	0,38	0,49	0,54	0,48	0,07	0,21	0,20	0,28	0,23	0,04	
17 Hubert Sauzeau 2	14,0	2	7,0	5	0,58	0,77	0,85	0,77	0,13	0,29	0,30	0,38	0,32	0,05	
18 Charles Müller	31,3	5	20,3	6	0,27	0,34	0,44	0,35	0,07	0,15	0,16	0,11	0,14	0,03	
19 Furcy de Lavault	23,5	2	14,5	7	0,32	0,42	0,66	0,48	0,16	0,18	0,18	0,15	0,17	0,02	
20 Louis Alexandre Cabié	11,7	1	9,7	1	0,62	0,72	0,96	0,73	0,16	0,40	0,33	0,42	0,38	0,05	
21 Louis Lessieux	21,0	4	12,0	5	0,37	0,46	0,61	0,48	0,11	0,15	0,15	0,13	0,14	0,01	
22 Jeannine Gilles-Murique	8,0	2	5,0	1	0,95	1,03	1,57	1,08	0,31	0,33	0,37	0,40	0,37	0,04	
23 Night Watch mockup canvas	20,0	2	14,3	3	0,41	0,72	0,74	0,69	0,16	0,28	0,27	0,27	0,27	0,01	
24 "pattina" lining canvas	9,0	2	6,0	1	0,37	0,42	0,51	0,42	0,07	0,37	0,31	0,24	0,31	0,07	
25 "patta" lining canvas	7,0	1	3,0	3	0,54	0,76	0,94	0,81	0,17	0,33	0,39	0,39	0,37	0,03	
26 canvassing "03f"	12,0	1	9,0	2	0,62	0,71	0,85	0,73	0,13	0,46	0,54	0,50	0,50	0,04	

WEFT yarn width		dimensional classes numerosity				yarn width means					yarn thickness				
sample name	th. count	S	M	L	S mean	M mean	L mean	w. mean	st. dev.	mean 1	mean 2	mean 3	weft	st. dev.	
1 plain canvas 1	13,5	3	5,5	5	0,38	0,41	0,55	0,46	0,08	0,23	0,24	0,20	0,22	0,02	
2 plain canvas 2	8,0	1	6,0	1	0,58	0,71	1,13	0,75	0,26	0,32	0,41	0,50	0,41	0,09	
3 plain canvas 3	12,0	1	9,0	2	0,36	0,59	0,98	0,64	0,28	0,46	0,45	-	0,46	0,01	
4 plain canvas 4	7,0	1	4,0	2	0,67	0,97	1,11	0,97	0,21	0,48	0,48	0,36	0,44	0,07	
5 plain canvas 5	11,0	2	7,0	2	0,47	0,59	0,77	0,60	0,13	0,44	0,43	0,52	0,46	0,05	
6 Domenico C. Malinconico	13,3	3	6,3	4	0,32	0,50	0,57	0,48	0,12	0,22	0,28	0,29	0,26	0,04	
7 Bernard d'Agesci	17,0	2	10,0	5	0,27	0,48	0,50	0,46	0,11	0,18	0,18	0,21	0,19	0,02	
8 medium paste lining canvas (IT)	8,0	2	4,0	2	0,53	0,79	0,97	0,77	0,21	0,30	0,23	0,46	0,33	0,12	
9 heavy paste lining canvas (IT)	7,0	1	5,0	1	0,47	0,81	0,81	0,76	0,17	0,48	0,56	-	0,52	0,06	
10 Fragonard medium paste lining	11,3	1	7,3	3	0,33	0,73	0,76	0,70	0,21	0,28	0,33	0,29	0,30	0,03	
11 Raffaele Postiglione	8,0	1	5,0	2	0,54	0,97	1,12	0,96	0,27	0,40	0,34	0,37	0,37	0,03	
12 Alfred Dehodencq	11,0	2	7,0	2	0,32	0,54	0,62	0,51	0,14	0,28	0,35	0,33	0,32	0,04	
13 Jules Gélibert	18,7	1	16,7	1	0,34	0,40	0,53	0,41	0,10	0,22	0,22	0,24	0,23	0,01	
14 Louis Augustin Auguin	25,3	2	21,3	2	0,31	0,32	0,46	0,33	0,07	0,31	0,28	0,29	0,29	0,02	
15 Ludovic Alleaume	21,7	2	16,7	3	0,28	0,34	0,40	0,35	0,06	0,16	0,16	0,18	0,17	0,01	
16 Hubert Sauzeau 1	20,0	3	14,0	3	0,37	0,41	0,40	0,40	0,05	0,23	0,23	0,24	0,23	0,01	
17 Hubert Sauzeau 2	12,0	2	8,0	2	0,50	0,46	0,63	0,50	0,08	0,32	0,33	0,39	0,35	0,04	
18 Charles Müller	29,0	5	20,0	4	0,19	0,31	0,40	0,30	0,09	0,11	0,16	0,14	0,14	0,03	
19 Furcy de Lavault	22,3	4	12,3	6	0,24	0,34	0,49	0,36	0,12	0,18	0,17	0,30	0,22	0,07	
20 Louis Alexandre Cabié	10,8	2	5,8	3	0,61	0,71	1,18	0,82	0,27	0,43	0,44	0,56	0,48	0,07	
21 Louis Lessieux	21,0	7	12,0	2	0,24	0,29	0,42	0,29	0,09	0,22	0,17	0,13	0,17	0,05	
22 Jeannine Gilles-Murique	8,0	1	6,0	1	1,11	1,06	1,64	1,14	0,31	0,47	0,45	0,44	0,45	0,02	
23 Night Watch mockup canvas	16,0	3	11,3	3	0,49	0,45	0,51	0,46	0,03	0,31	0,32	0,31	0,31	0,01	
24 "pattina" lining canvas	9,0	1	7,0	1	0,27	0,47	0,58	0,46	0,14	0,38	0,30	0,27	0,32	0,06	
25 "patta" lining canvas	5,0	1	2,0	2	0,60	0,76	0,87	0,77	0,13	0,41	0,36	0,47	0,41	0,06	
26 canvassing "03f"	7,0	1	5,0	1	0,61	0,66	0,79	0,67	0,08	0,47	0,42	0,48	0,46	0,03	

Table 4. The relative dimension subsets, the mean values and the weighted mean of the yarn width observations; the mean thickness of the yarns and their standard deviation values.

Figure 7. The measures of the yarn's width weighted mean. The difference shows that the warp yarns are wider in 80% of the 26 canvases.

In fig. 8 the thickness of the yarns in the two directions is compared, and we see that in 19 cases out of 26 (73%) the weft yarns are thicker than the warp, despite their lower width. If the subset under the pale blue band is not included, the prevalence becomes 70% (14 over 20 textiles). This apparently surprising information further confirms the role of twist in maintaining the original circular shape of the yarn, as the weft yarns have a higher TPM value.

Figure 8. Weft yarns are thicker than the warp yarns in 70% of the cases, because they retain a more circular section during weaving.

In fig. 9 the elliptical cross-sectional area of the yarns is plotted, and shows a slight prevalence of the warp (15 over 11, or 58%). In the 13 cases under the pale blue band, the differences are very shallow:

between 0.016 mm^2 and -0.016 mm^2 . If the subset is excluded, the prevalence of the warp is reduced to 54%. This would bring to the conclusion that the yarns are originally only slightly different in the two directions and that the larger width value of the warp yarns is acquired during weaving. Still, the differences in twist (which is not affected by the weaving process) confirm the previous assumptions about the intentional choice of larger yarns for the warp direction. The correlation between twist values and yarn dimensions will be further discussed in next paragraph.

Figure 9. The area of the elliptical cross section in warp and weft yarns, higher in the warp in 54% of the cases.

Twist per meter

The amount of twist that natural fibres undergo during the spinning process depends on the characteristics of the fibre strand, which are highly variable [Kania, 2013]. Thinner fibre strands will twist more than a bulkier flock, stiffer sections will twist less, and yarns show different twist and width along their length. “Twist goes where the yarns are thinner”, as a traditional spinner would say, and the correlation between TPM and yarn linear density is well known in textile engineering [Saville, 99; Neckář and Das, 2018]. The data in table 5 describe the correlation existing between yarn width and TPM, analysing the difference found between the dimensional subsets of yarns. The yarn width and its TPM value were measured at the same location, and each of the values is the mean of three locations on the same yarn. Within the area of observation in the samples, the thinner yarns (class S) have a higher TPM value, and the wider yarns have a lower TPM value. The difference between the Small and the Large class TPM values is always a positive number, and the % difference in TPM is correlated to the % difference measured in the yarn width. In table 6 yarn width and TPM weighted means values in warp and weft are shown, explaining why the weft yarns have a higher TPM value, as they are often thinner. A correlation similar to that seen in fig. 6 for the higher yarn width in the warp (80%) would be expected, but we find instead a weaker one, since it verifies in only 17 cases out of 26 (or 65%). However, it should be noted that in 5 of the 9 cases where the TPM is higher in the warp yarns, this is actually due to the fact that they happen to be thinner than the weft yarns. In addition, the specimens have other unusual morphological characteristics: n. 8 and n. 24 are very open weave canvases used for lining, with yarns of equal width and thickness in both directions; n. 20 and n. 22 are more recent historical textiles (n. 20 has thin cotton warp and thicker hemp weft), both apparently designed for painting, with limited space between the flat yarns (high cover factor).

WARP		Warp yarn width				Warp TPM				twist
sample name	Small	Medium	Large	% Large-Small	Small	Medium	Large	% Small-Large	Z or S	
1 plain canvas 1	0,30	0,43	0,67	55%	374,89	264,12	218,77	42%	Z	
2 plain canvas 2	0,56	0,79	1,17	52%	304,32	115,02	145,29	52%	Z	
3 plain canvas 3	0,53	0,87	1,00	47%	298,24	143,08	124,82	58%	Z	
4 plain canvas 4	0,53	0,76	1,16	54%	291,42	190,29	101,61	65%	Z	
5 plain canvas 5	0,39	0,59	0,87	55%	321,07	335,95	180,68	44%	Z	
6 Domenico C. Malinconico	0,43	0,72	0,80	46%	438,67	144,33	134,33	69%	Z	
7 Bernard d'Agesci	0,28	0,34	0,58	51%	515,59	184,70	173,96	66%	Z	
8 medium paste lining canvas (IT)	0,62	0,70	1,11	44%	318,98	235,03	136,80	57%	Z	
9 heavy paste lining canvas (IT)	0,81	1,18	1,39	42%	180,63	224,10	115,18	36%	Z	
10 Fragonard medium paste lining	0,23	0,74	0,88	74%	394,21	186,25	153,44	61%	Z	
11 Raffaele Postiglione	0,41	0,61	0,76	46%	310,29	221,07	196,94	37%	Z	
12 Alfred Dehodencq	0,47	0,69	0,94	50%	253,23	150,43	158,78	37%	Z	
13 Jules Gélibert	0,40	0,49	0,53	24%	280,13	244,90	193,09	31%	Z	
14 Louis Augustin Auguin	0,33	0,38	0,50	35%	357,51	330,46	228,35	36%	Z	
15 Ludovic Alleaume	0,30	0,43	0,54	44%	208,60	229,98	140,43	33%	Z	
16 Hubert Sauzeau 1	0,38	0,49	0,54	29%	286,27	274,22	253,60	11%	Z	
17 Hubert Sauzeau 2	0,58	0,77	0,85	32%	359,85	216,34	162,85	55%	Z	
18 Charles Müller	0,27	0,34	0,44	39%	423,32	407,67	158,34	63%	Z	
19 Furcy de Lavault	0,32	0,42	0,66	52%	330,62	221,19	133,43	60%	Z	
20 Louis Alexandre Cabié	0,62	0,72	0,96	36%	272,36	253,29	186,41	32%	Z	
21 Louis Lessieux	0,37	0,46	0,61	40%	312,33	252,49	214,17	31%	Z	
22 Jeannine Gilles-Murique	0,95	1,03	1,57	39%	142,19	122,07	104,93	26%	Z	
23 Night Watch mockup canvas	0,41	0,72	0,74	44%	183,57	156,32	176,82	4%	Z	
24 "pattina" lining canvas	0,37	0,42	0,51	27%	371,56	281,37	196,09	47%	Z	
25 "patta" lining canvas	0,54	0,76	0,94	43%	238,53	153,66	101,13	58%	Z	
26 canvassing "03f"	0,62	0,71	0,85	28%	191,06	163,57	125,27	34%	Z	

WEFT		Weft yarn width				Weft TPM				twist
sample name	Small	Medium	Large	% Large-Small	Small	Medium	Large	% Small-Large	Z or S	
1 plain canvas 1	0,38	0,41	0,55	30%	248,47	260,98	207,32	17%	Z	
2 plain canvas 2	0,58	0,71	1,13	49%	205,37	161,43	119,35	42%	Z	
3 plain canvas 3	0,36	0,59	0,98	64%	296,26	251,11	99,61	66%	Z	
4 plain canvas 4	0,67	0,97	1,11	40%	172,27	134,03	117,80	32%	Z	
5 plain canvas 5	0,47	0,59	0,77	39%	243,86	170,24	125,13	49%	Z	
6 Domenico C. Malinconico	0,32	0,50	0,57	44%	393,67	145,00	134,67	66%	Z	
7 Bernard d'Agesci	0,27	0,48	0,50	47%	293,05	289,28	163,69	44%	Z	
8 medium paste lining canvas (IT)	0,53	0,79	0,97	45%	185,45	218,86	141,94	23%	Z	
9 heavy paste lining canvas (IT)	0,47	0,80	0,81	42%	475,24	222,37	171,52	64%	Z	
10 Fragonard medium paste lining	0,33	0,73	0,76	57%	268,46	131,10	166,60	38%	Z	
11 Raffaele Postiglione	0,54	0,97	1,12	52%	201,35	150,00	85,68	57%	Z	
12 Alfred Dehodencq	0,32	0,54	0,62	49%	403,85	174,84	150,46	63%	Z	
13 Jules Gélibert	0,34	0,40	0,53	36%	234,11	297,55	192,11	18%	Z	
14 Louis Augustin Auguin	0,31	0,32	0,46	32%	513,44	472,33	333,78	35%	Z	
15 Ludovic Alleaume	0,28	0,34	0,40	31%	270,39	251,86	231,90	14%	Z	
16 Hubert Sauzeau 1	0,37	0,41	0,40	8%	344,41	392,71	266,18	23%	Z	
17 Hubert Sauzeau 2	0,50	0,46	0,63	21%	223,28	239,23	138,78	38%	Z	
18 Charles Müller	0,19	0,31	0,40	53%	473,04	385,82	241,81	49%	Z	
19 Furcy de Lavault	0,24	0,34	0,49	51%	541,13	354,36	175,30	68%	Z	
20 Louis Alexandre Cabié	0,61	0,71	1,18	48%	191,07	198,97	94,84	50%	Z	
21 Louis Lessieux	0,24	0,29	0,42	43%	444,86	353,41	224,57	50%	Z	
22 Jeannine Gilles-Murique	1,11	1,06	1,64	32%	93,10	56,92	80,82	13%	Z	
23 Night Watch mockup canvas	0,49	0,45	0,51	3%	249,46	261,26	229,32	8%	Z	
24 "pattina" lining canvas	0,27	0,47	0,58	53%	358,79	174,71	177,12	51%	Z	
25 "patta" lining canvas	0,60	0,76	0,87	31%	195,86	168,90	133,92	32%	Z	
26 canvassing "03f"	0,61	0,66	0,79	22%	197,55	161,24	136,53	31%	Z	

Table 5. Warp and weft TPM in function of the yarn width. TPM is higher for the thinner yarns.

	sample name	yarn width w. means		TPM w. means		
		warp width	weft width	warp TPM	weft TPM	weft-warp
1	plain canvas 1	0,47	0,46	277,10	238,33	-38,77
2	plain canvas 2	0,87	0,75	140,48	161,66	21,18
3	plain canvas 3	0,87	0,64	150,43	229,62	79,20
4	plain canvas 4	0,80	0,97	193,05	134,86	-58,20
5	plain canvas 5	0,64	0,60	286,19	175,42	-110,77
6	Domenico C. Malinconico	0,70	0,48	186,54	197,85	11,31
7	Bernard d'Agesci	0,39	0,46	200,12	252,78	52,66
8	medium paste lining canvas (IT)	0,79	0,77	230,95	191,28	-39,67
9	heavy paste lining canvas (IT)	1,19	0,75	193,95	251,23	57,28
10	Fragonard medium paste lining	0,72	0,70	196,67	152,62	-44,05
11	Raffaele Postiglione	0,60	0,96	229,20	140,34	-88,86
12	Alfred Dehodencq	0,71	0,51	163,99	212,05	48,06
13	Jules Gélibert	0,49	0,41	244,21	288,50	44,29
14	Louis Augustin Auguin	0,39	0,33	324,45	464,63	140,17
15	Ludovic Alleaume	0,44	0,35	213,28	250,80	37,53
16	Hubert Sauzeau 1	0,48	0,40	272,11	366,49	94,38
17	Hubert Sauzeau 2	0,77	0,50	217,74	219,83	2,09
18	Charles Müller	0,35	0,30	362,42	380,99	18,57
19	Furcy de Lavault	0,48	0,36	204,36	339,70	135,34
20	Louis Alexandre Cabié	0,73	0,82	249,19	168,68	-80,51
21	Louis Lessieux	0,48	0,29	254,77	371,62	116,86
22	Jeannine Gilles-Murique	1,08	1,14	124,96	64,43	-60,52
23	Night Watch mockup canvas	0,69	0,46	162,12	253,06	90,94
24	"pattina" lining canvas	0,42	0,46	291,94	195,43	-96,51
25	"patta" lining canvas	0,81	0,77	143,27	160,30	17,03
26	canvassing "03F"	0,73	0,67	159,48	162,90	3,42

Table 6. TPM and yarn width weighted means. In 17 cases, or 65%, warp has higher TPM, red values do not follow the general trend.

The degree of yarn compression (or the width over the thickness of the yarn) appears to be directly correlated with the quantity of twist in the yarns, as we see in fig. 10 where the z axis compression is compared with the TPM. Higher twist means better cohesion of the yarn and higher friction between the fibres, both implying a higher retention of the original circular section, and for this reason the weft yarns generally have lower z axis compression.

Figure 10. The yarn compression on the z axis of the textile (yarn width over thickness) and TPM. Higher TPM implies lower yarn compression.

Crimp % value

The measures of crimp in warp and weft found in table 7 and in fig. 11, provide a rather uncontroversial information about the prevalence of crimp in the warp direction in our specimens, since it is higher in 24 of the 26 cases. Warp crimp is on average 50% higher than weft crimp, exceeding 64% in 10 cases and less than 23% in only one case. The reason for such a large difference is that the weft yarn inserted between the warps causes them to bend during the shedding process, creating a crimped shape that becomes permanent in the woven canvas. Such a crimped shape is maintained by the friction and internal tensions between the yarns. As it is usually reduced after wetting and/or stretching of the fabric, we can assume that the crimp values in the historical textiles studied here were probably higher at the origin.

sample name	crimp % measures						means		difference
	warp 1	weft 1	warp 2	weft 2	warp 3	weft 3	warp	weft	warp-weft
1 plain canvas 1	7,69	5,35	8,39	5,78	7,65	5,73	7,91	5,62	2,29
2 plain canvas 2	11,42	3,65	15,38	6,85	9,39	2,44	12,06	4,31	7,75
3 plain canvas 3	8,68	6,45	5,79	5,17	7,46	5,16	7,31	5,59	1,72
4 plain canvas 4	16,3	2,04	8,41	2,05	8,39	2,45	11,03	2,18	8,85
5 plain canvas 5	24,01	1,56	28,11	2,7	12,95	1,77	21,69	2,01	19,68
6 Domenico C. Malinconico	10,35	3,67	9,45	4,18	13,55	5,02	11,12	4,29	6,83
7 Bernard d'Agesci	4,73	10,22	6,82	3,99	7,56	7,65	6,37	7,29	-0,92
8 medium paste lining canvas (IT)	2,28	2,16	0,93	3,59	2,77	1,7	1,99	2,48	-0,49
9 heavy paste lining canvas (IT)	14,09	8,11	14,46	10,95	11,15	9,42	13,23	9,49	3,74
10 Fragonard medium paste lining	8,78	2,66	8,21	3,4	7,81	2,47	8,27	2,84	5,42
11 Raffaele Postiglione	8,09	2,49	2,93	4,25	4,45	3,06	5,16	3,27	1,89
12 Alfred Dehodencq	15,51	2,78	14,87	2,45	15,5	1,78	15,29	2,34	12,96
13 Jules Gélibert	12,3	3,4	11,36	3,58	12,1	3,71	11,92	3,56	8,36
14 Louis Augustin Auguin	17,67	5,8	13,78	3,87	7,44	4,28	12,96	4,65	8,31
15 Ludovic Alleaume	9,71	6,54	11,82	8,62	12,56	5,11	11,36	6,76	4,61
16 Hubert Sauzeau 1	13,28	6,38	9,54	5,63	18,14	5,18	13,65	5,73	7,92
17 Hubert Sauzeau 2	19,08	5,12	20,47	5,84	19,45	7,05	19,67	6,00	13,66
18 Charles Müller	11,82	4,96	8,49	6,47	10,48	5,66	10,26	5,70	4,57
19 Furcy de Lavault	13,68	3	14,28	3,63	14,66	2,45	14,21	3,03	11,18
20 Louis Alexandre Cabié	11,25	3,3	9,62	3,11	-	-	10,44	3,21	7,23
21 Louis Lessieux	11,9	5,09	13,27	7,38	15,94	6,44	13,70	6,30	7,40
22 Jeannine Gilles-Murique	7,72	3,92	5,07	3,81	-	-	6,40	3,87	2,53
23 Night Watch mockup canvas	7,03	1,04	7,63	2,63	6,83	1,06	7,16	1,58	5,59
24 "pattina" lining canvas	2,93	0,72	2,45	1,42	3,44	2,59	2,94	1,58	1,36
25 "patta" lining canvas	3	1,65	1,94	2,17	1,85	2,18	2,26	2,00	0,26
26 canvassing "03F"	5,69	2,59	5,86	2,59	4,91	2,34	5,48	2,51	2,98

Table 7. Crimp measures and their analysis.

Figure 11. Crimp values in the warp are higher than in the weft in 92% of the cases.

Discussion

Characteristics correlated to warp and weft

Within the set of 22 historical and 4 modern textiles, the analysis of the quantified morphological characteristics of the yarns shows recurring features correlated with the weaving directions. The most relevant are listed in table 8, and the presence of a higher crimp in the warp provides the strongest correlation (92%). A similarly high prevalence of warp crimp is also found in the literature, both in conservation [Young and Jardine, 2012; Flock, 2020] and textile engineering [Mertova et al. 16]. Warp yarns are also wider (80%) and have a higher thread-count (77%) than the weft yarns, providing additional useful indicators. These seem to be directly related to the convenience of weaving practice, as it is easier and cheaper to produce a balanced textile with more warp yarns, which are wider to avoid them breaking during the weaving process. The weft threads, on the other hand, are easy to reconnect as they are simply left in the shed, and this is done each time the shuttle needs to be refilled. The consistency of the features revealed by this study allows direct correlations with manufacturing techniques, and apply to both hand-woven and industrial textiles. Experience gained during the research has shown that the difference in crimp is often clear enough to make predictions about the weft and warp directions by naked eye observation. All other features require more detailed observation and the measurements obtained with the methods described.

The higher twist in the weft yarns follows the rule that thinner yarns have higher twist. The z-axis compression of the yarns is closely related to the amount of twist in the yarns, and the warp yarns take on a wider elliptical shape when bent over the weft. This is shown by the fact that the warp yarns have more z-compression in 73 % of the cases and less twist in 65% of the cases.

higher value	crimp	yarn width	thread count	z compression	twist
warp	92%	80%	77%	73%	35%
weft	8%	20%	23%	27%	65%

Table 8. General correlations with warp and weft in the 26 specimens.

The recent introduction of automated measuring algorithms and artificial intelligence to the analysis of images of the textile supports of canvas painting has allowed to obtain quantitative measurements of the direction and frequency of the yarns, highlighting recurring patterns and irregularities [Johnson, et al., 2013; Nobel et al., 2018]. Unfortunately, to the present date, yarn width and thickness, crimp and twist can only be measured by visual inspection and it is not yet possible to map them on the textile with automated processes.

A mostly non-destructive observation protocol was developed, which makes it possible to extract quantitative data from a limited sample size. The data collected and analysed in the present research is based on the observation of relatively small samples, due to the decision to observe samples from historical textiles and obtain unambiguous correlations with their tensile response. Having obtained useful data from small samples appears to be useful for the field of conservation and conservation science.

Warp and weft correlations in the literature

The following literature review aims to describe the most relevant approaches to the specific problem of warp and weft identification in historical textiles since the 1990s. It is not intended to be comprehensive, aiming to describe a few of the well-known contributions about the identification of warp and weft, and about the morphological description of the woven structures of canvas supports.

Rouba proposed experience-based methods to identify warp from weft by visually examining the reverse of the painting [Rouba, 1992]. Her descriptions define the warp yarns as being strictly parallel, while the weft yarns are sometimes curved and show discontinuities or marks made when the weft was cast on and beaten with the comb. She noted that the warp yarns are usually of better quality, woven regularly and without defects, and may outnumber the weft yarns in thread count. Van de Wetering and Bosshard observed the canvas paintings supports structure through their X-ray images, to investigate the origin of the textiles and to identify warp from weft [van de Wetering, 1997]. The X-ray observation method allowed defining yarn orientation and density, local thickenings and deviations from straightness. They found that warp count is more consistent and often higher than the weft. The weft yarns were instead found to be of poorer quality, showing frequent thickenings, and accumulations of loose fibres on the warp cause the weft to bend over. The weft also showed recurring irregularities in the weave, such as stripes of uneven density caused by the beating of the comb or by the rolling of the fabric. The weft also showed recurring irregularities in the weave, such as stripes of uneven density caused by the beating of the comb or the rolling of the fabric. Van de Wetering and Bosshard, and also Rouba, suggested that the warp yarns had more twist and less crimp, but they did not measure these characteristics and the authors openly made a hypothesis.

Recent investigations using algorithms and artificial intelligence to describe the thread count and angle maps in warp and weft have made it possible to determine correlations between textile pieces belonging to different paintings [van der Maaten and Erdmann, 2015]. The X-ray observation method is similar to van der Wetering's studies, but the incomparably higher analytical capacity associated with the technology allows for a much deeper understanding.²³ As the research was extended to 400 van Gogh paintings [Johnson et al., 2013], it also allowed for statistical studies. The overall correlations with warp and weft directions offered by these methods are similar to those deriving from van der Wetering's work. In [Murashov, et al., 2019], similar results are obtained using raking light instead of X-ray or transmitted light observations. In the textile industry, automated methods to measure thread densities from simple images of the fabric are being developed [Pan et al, 2015; Aldemir et al., 2019]. Reliable correlations with warp and weft directions, and therefore their identification when a selvedge is not available, are also made available, based on the variability of the thread count and the thread angle within the textile. Although very useful for technical art history (and for industrial inspection), to the date, these methods cannot measure the twist and crimp of the yarns, nor their width. The maps of the painting support they generate may be integrated with the numerical data about the yarn characteristics provided by the research presented here, describing the structure needed for powerful digital simulations.

Conclusions and future work

Effective and relatively simple methods to measure usually inaccessible characteristics of historical textiles have been developed, organized and described in this paper. The protocols were tested on a heterogeneous group of samples, and the quantity of data allowed drawing a preliminary set of conclusions that will be challenged by the future steps of the research, on a much wider set of specimens. It is interesting to note that strong correlations have been found for warp and weft yarns that promise a certain degree of reliability in their identification in the absence of a selvedge.

The future step is to test a larger number of historical textiles, that are already being prepared. Statistical analysis will show the correlation between the observation of a specific characteristic of

²³ <https://countingvermeer.rkdstudies.nl/6-exploiting-weave-maps/>

the yarns and the possibility to identify of the warp and weft in the absence of a selvage, and how the probability is increased by the simultaneous observation of more than one characteristic. The other direction of the ongoing research is on the mechanical side, performing uniaxial and biaxial tensile tests on the observed specimens in order to build a correlation database with the characteristics studied here.

Glossary of terms

- **Fibres.** Long, thin, flexible strands of material that can be spun into yarn or thread, used in the production of textiles and fabrics.
- **Thread.** A yarn that is usually thin and highly twisted, adapted for sewing. Thread and yarn can be considered synonyms.
- **Yarn.** General definition of a long strand of twisted fibres used for weaving. Yarn and thread can be considered synonyms, but yarn was preferred because it is a more general term. For the definition of the number of yarns per unit length of the textile, the term “thread count” was chosen because it is of general use and changing it to “yarn count” sounded unnatural.
- **Twist.** During the spinning process, the fibre strands are wound around their axis, thereby acquiring twist. High twist means high tensile strength and cohesion of the yarn.
- **Warp.** The longitudinal yarns that are held in tension on a loom during the weaving process. They run parallel to the length of the fabric and serve as the foundation or backbone of the woven fabric.
- **Weft.** The transversal yarns that weave in and out of the warp yarns to make fabric during the shedding process.
- **Shedding, shed.** Process where the warp yarns are divided into sets to create an open space, or shed, through which the weft yarn is passed.
- **Crimp.** The waviness or bending of yarns within a fabric as they interlace with each other. It describes how much the yarns deviate from a straight line as they bend over and under other yarns. The crimp is usually expressed as the percentage of the extra length of the interlaced yarn in relation to the straight yarn.
- **Plain weave.** The pattern alternates every row, so the warp and weft interlace 1:1 at right angles, creating a uniform texture.
- **Basket weave.** The pattern is the same as in plain weave, but multiple warp and weft threads (usually two or more) are woven together as a unit, rather than individually.

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Authorship contribution statement

Antonio Iaccarino Idelson: Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Investigation, Validation, Writing.

Roger Groves and Otto Bergsma: Supervision, review & editing.

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